

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

ECOLOGICAL-ECONOMIC ASSESSMENT OF THE NATURAL-RESOURCE POTENTIAL OF GANJA-DASKASEN ECONOMIC DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

The city of Ganja is considered the socio-economic base of the western region of Azerbaijan. During the transition period, due to economic difficulties, the operation of most industrial enterprises in the city was disrupted, which affected the demographic and socio-economic potential. Despite the economic reforms, some socio-economic problems still remain, there are difficulties in providing employment to the population and raising the level of socio-cultural services. Cities and regional centers are unable to accommodate all migrants from neighboring areas, resulting in population outflows from the region as a whole. The emerging problems require the deepening of economic reforms.

Keywords: socio-economic potential, demographic potential, industrial structure, natural resource potential, socio-economic potential.

Introduction. Cities are the centers of socio-economic and demographic development of the country and its individual regions. They have a special role in the use of natural resources, in the processing of agricultural products, and in providing employment to the population. Increasing the role of regions in the socio-economic development of the country, regulating population migration from regions to capitals and foreign countries depends to a certain extent on the number and economic potential of cities acting as regional and regional centers [1].

Most of the social service institutions and enterprises operate in cities. Therefore, the population of the city and surrounding regions can fully meet their daily needs.

Economic-geographic location (EGP), transport-communication networks, human resources allow to form a socio-economic base in a certain area in a short period of time, which in turn forms cities or industrial hubs with different industrial structures.

Urban settlements in Azerbaijan can be divided into 2 groups. One group includes "historical" cities: Baku, Ganja, Shamakhi, Nakhchivan, Ordubad, Barda, Sheki, etc. The second group includes cities and towns created in the 20th and 21st centuries. During the development of the oil industry and later the creation of other sectors of the economy. The 20-30s and 50-60s of the 20th century are distinguished by the special period of the creation of new cities and their development. [1; 2].

Despite the lack of administrative control, these cities: "attract" migrants from surrounding regions; the entire republic manages significant light and food industry enterprises, processing agricultural products grown in nearby rural areas.

Object and methods of research. The city of Ganja is located in the west of the Republic of Azerbaijan. It is the main center of the region due to its population and socio-economic potential. 3.4% of the country's population lives in cities, including 6.4% of the urban population. In the Ganja-Gazakh economic district, these numbers make up 26.1 percent of the total population, and 56.9 percent of the urban population.

The city is located on the Ganja-Kazakh plain and is the main transport hub through which the Baku-Kazakh road and railways pass, connecting the country's capital with seaports located on the Black Sea coast of Georgia.

There are 7 villages under the administrative control of Ganja city. They were created quite recently, so their population is small. Meh-sati (14.3 thousand people) and Sadili (11.2 thousand people) villages stand out among them [3. P. 83].

In different years, the territorial organization of the country's population and economy was studied by Azerbaijani scientists. They studied the economic-geographic base and socio-demographic situation of cities of different sizes and different economic regions. Their research has shown that economic regions have favorable natural-geographical conditions for development, natural resources and demographic potential.

However, certain problems arose in the development of cities and the operation of production and service enterprises during the transition period. Some of them are closed, most of them are not working at full capacity. The decrease in agricultural production deprived enterprises of raw materials and semi-finished products. As a result, the population lost jobs and sources of income. In many farm facilities, the equipment is outdated, and the manufactured products do not meet modern requirements; economic relations have been severed and their restoration requires enormous effort and financial and technical resources. Privatization is proceeding at a slow pace. In the current conditions, it is necessary to take measures related to the restoration of previously existing production and service enterprises in the cities and towns of the republic, as well as the construction of new facilities. For this, it is necessary to use local natural resources and natural conditions, to develop the construction of new industrial enterprises by using new high-tech technologies, taking into account the needs of the country's economy, its population, and the markets of neighboring countries.

Demographic potential. The city of Ganja is one of the historical cities of the country. But in terms of population and socio-economic potential, it lags far behind the city of Baku. Starting in the 20s and 30s in the city. In the 20th century, several food and light industrial enterprises were built for the processing of agricultural products [5].

The economic growth of the city helped to increase its demographic potential. And this process in the second half of the twentieth century. It was fast until the 1970s. In 1959, there were 136.4 thousand people in the city. By 1970, the population increased by 39.0% and reached 189.5 thousand people [8].

In the next 10-year period, the population growth decreased by 22.4% and in 1979 it was 231.9 thousand people. During the transition period, economic difficulties, a decrease in the standard of living, and the loss of jobs had a negative impact on the birth rate - it decreased several times. At the same time, migration activity has also increased. The current demographic situation has reduced the population growth in Ganja. For the period 1989-1999, the population of the city increased by 6.7%, which is 3 times less than in the previous 10-year period [1].

In the 80s of the XX century. In the city of Ganja, the birth rate per 1000 people was 22.2 ppm, the rate of natural growth was 15.9 per thousand [12]. Since the early 1990s. Due to the difficulties of the transition period, these numbers gradually decreased. Thus, in 1990, the absolute birth rate was 5863 people, and the natural increase was 4416 people. In the following years, a continuous decrease in growth is observed. In 2010-2015, these numbers increased to the level of the 1990s.

In 1999-2009. The population of the city increased by 14.0 thousand people (4.7%) and reached 313.3 thousand people. In the following years, the population growth rate was 19.3 thousand people or 6.1% [6; eleven].

However, in the last few years, there has been a decline in the birth rate and natural population growth. In 2017, the birth rate in the city was 3359 people, natural increase was 1273 people. They are 2.0 and 3.9 times less than in 2011, respectively. During this period, the rate of natural growth per 1000 people decreased from 15.5 to 3.8 ppm. Today, the death rate in the city (6.3 per 1000 people) is higher than the national average (6.1) [3].

Employment. Recently, the employment structure in Ganja city has changed radically. According to the 2009 census, the number of economically active population in the city was 139.3 thousand people. The service sector took the leading place in the employment structure. In 2009, 79.9 thousand people (57.4 percent of the employed) worked in enterprises of this industry. The high level of employment in these industries is related to the operation of numerous commercial and public catering facilities, and the rapid development of the social services network.

The second place in the structure of employment in the city belongs to the construction industry. 21.3 thousand people are employed here (special 15.3%). In this period of economic reforms, large-scale construction works are being carried out in the city: educational,

health and cultural facilities are put into use, a metallurgical plant is being built, etc.

The city is the main transport hub in the west of the country. Transport and communication lines pass through the area. Therefore, 10.4 percent of the economically active population is engaged in this industry, and in absolute terms there are 14.5 thousand people.

The decline in production and disruption of most industrial enterprises reduced the specific weight of employment in this area. Despite the measures taken, industrial employment in the city remains at a very low level. Despite the strong industrial potential in the city, most of the enterprises in this industry are not working at full capacity, and some have closed. Therefore, employment in the industry is steadily decreasing year by year. In 2005, 11.2 thousand people were employed in the industrial enterprises of the city. By 2010, their number decreased to 7.1 thousand people. In 2014, their number was 6.2 thousand, and their share in the employment structure was close to 8.0 percent.

Urban lifestyle does not prevent a part of the population from growing crops. They live mainly in the outskirts of the city and in settlements that are administratively subordinate to the city. Their total number is 1739 people or 1.2% of employees. The population is mainly engaged in private farms, vegetable, melon and fruit growing. The implementation of agrarian reform to expand their farms and allowed to increase production in this industry.

Economic potential. The economic base in the city of Ganja was formed at the beginning of the 20th century. Food and light industrial enterprises were built in 1920-1930. They operated based on the processing of agricultural products and the production of cotton fiber, carpets, canned fruits and vegetables, meat and dairy products.

The city and Dashkasan region are one of the main metallurgical bases of the country. Zaglik alunite and iron ore deposits are located in Dashkasan district. The administrative district is located near the city of Ganja, and an aluminum plant was built in 1956 to exploit the alunite deposits, and the alunite produced here undergoes preliminary processing to obtain the final product later in Sumgait.

In the years of independence, a second aluminum plant was built in the city of Ganja. Both enterprises can independently process aluminum raw materials into final products. The raw material (bauxite alumina) for the plants is imported from Guinea or India, but provided that

There are certain problems with receiving cheap electricity. Therefore, the local raw material base is not used, both enterprises are not working at full capacity.

It should be noted that before that, iron ore was produced in the Dashkasan iron ore deposit since 1954. A mining and processing plant was built there. Then, the resulting concentrate was sent to Rustavi, Georgia for processing. After the independence of the two countries, these enterprises do not operate.

The economic relations between the cities of Ganja and Dashkasan, based on the use of metallurgical raw materials, were close and formed an industrial hub.

The development of this industrial center continues today. The new stage of improvement of the industrial structure is the construction of a new metallurgical and wagon-making plant in Ganja, as well as the expansion of the machine-building plant.

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